

Role of *Staphylococcus aureus* Biofilm in Teeth Plague and Mouth Infection in Al-Rifai District

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Abstract:

Staphylococcus aureus is one of the furthermost common microbes that can cause opportunistic infections, capable of inflicting potential life-threatening infections such as pneumonia, urinary tract infection, bloodstream infection, and infectious endocarditis. Biofilms are considered the common bacterial mode in the environment and are also, considered the Main cause of clinical and dental infections in our population. A total of 150 swabs from patients who have oral infections and plague from local hospitals and private clinics, then the specimens treated with microbiological and biochemical procedures are done to identify *S. aureus*. Three methods are used

for biofilms to be detected, CRA (Congo Red Agar method), TM (Tube method), and MtP (Microtiter plate method) the results of CRA can be shown by the appearance of colonies in 82% of the colonies' biofilm producers (slime) and 17.5% non-biofilm producer. In the TM and MtP methods, the results can shower by weak, moderate, and strong adhesive biofilm bacteria. antibiotics susceptibility was accomplished by disc distribution technique on sensitivity (Mulare Hinton) agar and observed High resistance to many antibiotics resulted in biofilm-forming and High sensitivity to other antibiotics.

Keywords: *Biofilm, Congo red agar, Staphylococci, oral cavity.*

Introduction

Staphylococcus aureus is a portion of human microflora capable of imposing potentially lethal infections such as bloodstream infections, urinary tract infections, and infective endocarditis (Irek et al. 2018)

Can cause the dominant oral pathogen in patients under intensive care treatment and

elderly patients under chronic care; The most communal dental diseases are gingivitis, periodontal disease, dental plague, pulpitis or pulp necrosis peripheral abscess (Scannapieco & Cantos 2016).

Staphylococcus's most important pathogenic factor is the capacity to form biofilm on polymeric surfaces.

Biofilm is defined as a multilayered cell cluster implanted in a matrix of extracellular polysaccharides (slime), substances that adhere to all surfaces either passive or living (Azmi, Adnan & Ab Malik, 2020)

Biofilms are the most communal form of bacterial growth in nature and are also imperative for dental infections which are common in our population; In the form of biofilm, *S. aureus* colonizes the teeth of patients. (Lipton, et al., 1993).

Biofilm formation is controlled by the gene product of *icaADBC* the of polysaccharide intracellular adhesin (PIA), which mediates cell-to-cell adhesion (Bose, et al., 2009)

Today the recognition of biofilms is difficult to eliminate and is ever so often resistant to systemic antibiotic therapy and the use of local technology to remove infected areas becomes necessary, the biofilms of *Streptococcus* on teeth are cariogenic and periodontal pathogenic bacteria (Lewis, 2001).

When bacteria in a biofilm have high resistance to antibiotics. In the case of gene transference from or to bacteria is known to be an imposing means by which virulence factors and antibiotic resistance share with the same and different species of bacteria (Marcus, et al., 2000).

The adjacent connection between bacteria and biofilm within the matrix prevents the diffusion of antibiotics via these folds (Jefferson, & Goldmann, 2005)

Aim of the Study

Our aim of the research was to determine the association between biofilm production and virulence of *S. aureus* in the oral cavity, its role in prominent oral diseases, and the role of biofilm in High antibiotic resistance of bacteria

Material and Method

Our study was performed in the Department of Animal Production in the agriculture college of Sumer University

A total of 120 clinical bacterial specimens from plague and gingal swabs from Al-Rifai's general

hospital and dental private clinic in the district. The specimens were held on transfer media then subculture on MacConkey agar and blood agar in 37°C in aerobic condition for 24 hrs, and the colony was observed. The biochemical test was done to identify the staphylococci.

To test antibiotic sensitivity by using the different discs of cefotaxime, ampicillin, vancomycin, tetracycline, Penicillin, and ciprofloxacin.

The biofilm production was detected by three detective methods: The microtiter plate method (MtP), The tube method (TM), and the Congo red Agar method (CRA).

Tube Method (TM)

Under septic conditions, sterilized plastic tubes were taken and filled with (trypticase soy broth TSB) 4 ml and inoculated with a loopful of microorganisms from overnight culture plates and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C (Mathur, et al., 2006).

After incubation, 4 ml of TSB with 4% glucose was added. Tubes were re-incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

The tubes were decanted and washed with PBS (pH 7.3). All tube was rinsed triple with Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS) with aseptic conditions to eradicate the boundless bacteria. To estimate the production of biofilm, the residual adherent was fixed with 2ml of methanol 99% for 15 minutes (optional step) and then stained with 0.1% crystal violet. The spare stain was detached and tubes were rinsed with deionized water, then dried aerobically.

Biofilm production was considered positive when a noticeable film lined the wall and bottom of the tube. Tubes were inspected and the amount of biofilm production was recorded as 0-absent, 1-weak, 2-moderate, or 3-strong. Tests were executed in triplicate and frequently three times.

Congo Red Agar Method (CRA)

The other method used to detect the formation of biofilm in staphylococci needs to use an especially sold medium called Congo red, This modified medium consists of brain heart

infusion broth (BHI 37gms/L) supplemented with 5% sucrose (50 gms/L), agar no.1 (10 gms/L), and Congo red dye (0.8 gms/L) (Melo, et al., 2013).

The stain was prepared separately as a concerted aqueous solution and disinfected by autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes, then added to additional medium ingredients and after the medium cooled to 55°C. Then the isolate was inoculated on plates and the plates were incubated for 24 to 48 hours at 37°C in aerobic condition.

A positive result was shown by dark colonies with a dry glassy surface. Poor(weak) slime producers generally persisted pink, though sporadic blackening centers of colonies were detected. Blackening of the colonies with the absence of a dry sparkly colonial morphology showed an unspecified result. The testing was executed in triple.

Microtiter Plate Method (MtP)

The microtiter plate method described by Christensen et al. (2001) and modified by the duration of incubation to more than 18 hrs extended to 24hrs and dilution to 1:40 according to the author.

In a new and polystyrene 96_well tissue culture plate fresh Culter diluted with trypticase soy broth (TSB) containing 0.25% glucose was added and incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hrs, Far along incubation all contented of the plate were gently detached by tapping, and washing by phosphate buffer saline three times to remove any plankton bacteria than the plate dried 1hour in room temperature and stained well by 1%

Crystal violet stain one minute and washing triple by distilled water and dried, to detect adherence biofilm bacteria must be reading in micro ELISA auto reader in at wavelength 570 nm (OD 750 nm) this OD value suitable to detected the adherence biofilm producer bacteria according to classification (Table 1) for individual strains of *Staphylococcus* spp (Baqai, et al., 2011).

Table 1. Classification of Bacterial Adherence by Microtiter Plate Method (MtP)

Mean OD values	Adherence	Biofilm formation
>0.240	Strong	High
0.120-0.240	Moderately	Moderate
<0.120	Non	Non or weak

Sensitivity test of antibiotics was done by traditional techniques via using the discs of penicillin, cefotaxime, ampicillin, vancomycin, tetracycline, and ciprofloxacin. (Bauer AW et al1966)

Results

In all 120 isolates, Biofilm creation has been informed in most *Staphylococcus* spp. Isolates in the Congo red agar method 82% (99) of the colonies grow like Black to red rough colonies and 17.5% (21) grow like red to orange crystalline surfaces the CRM showed variation results about other tests like the Table (2) showed.

Table 2. Shows the Production of Biofilm on the CRA Method

Congo red agar method	Slime (+)	Slime (-)	percentage
Red crystalline colonies	0	21	17.5%
Black rough colonies	99	0	82.5%
Total	99	21	100%

The Tube method has good results the biggest percentage of 49% (59) of all 120 isolates forming highly adhesive biofilm, and a quarter of

all 120 isolates 26% (31) and 25% (30) forming moderate and weak (non) adhesive biofilm respectively like the Table (3) showed.

Table 3. Shows the Production of Biofilm in the Tube Method (TM)

Tube method	Positive	Negative	Total	Percentage
High	59	0	59	49%
Moderate	31	0	31	26%
Weak (non)	0	30	30	25%

In the modified microtiter plate method (MtP) of a total of 120 isolates of biofilm formation *Staphylococcus* spp. Strong biofilm producers

72.5% (87), moderate biofilm producers 21.5% (25), and weak or non-biofilm producers 7% (8) as Table (4) shows.

Table 4. Shows the Production of Biofilm by the Microtiter Plate Method (MtP)

Biofilm forming	Number of isolates	Total	Percentage
Strong adherence	87	87	72.5%
Moderate adherence	25	25	21.5
Weak/nonadherence	8	8	7%

Figure 1. Shows the Antibiotic Sensitivity of *S. aureus* Pattern

Discussion

In our study isolated 120 of *S.aureus* and tested them by three different methods CRA, TM, and MtP we found that *S. aureus* was able to produce biofilm that is observed by other researchers. (O’Gara JP et al 2001.)

The biofilm-producer bacteria have high resistance to antibiotics that are observed by other, the closest contacted matrix and biofilm

that prevents reaching of antibiotic to exopolysaccharide matrix (Monroe D. 2007)

Biofilm producer bacteria showed exhibition and slow metabolism that is considered as a sensitivity to cell wall synthesis targeted antibiotics such as penicillin. Dental biofilm has high metabolism activity main reason to many dental plagues and other oral infections.(Rogers A H. 2008)

Conclusion

This resulted in poor hygiene and High carelessness in dental infection and plaque very common in our district and the whole country; that can cause biofilm production and antibiotic resistance. Dental biofilm can cause other systemic infections resulting from the surgical technique in the oral cavity or dental treatment.

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